

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

<https://llrjournal.com/index.php/11>

**INVESTIGATING LANGUAGE ANXIETY IN ONLINE
PRESENTATIONS: EXPERIENCES OF ESL UNDERGRADUATE
STUDENTS**

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Abstract

The paper examines the experiences of ESL undergraduates with language anxiety when making online presentations. The research aims to understand the sources of anxiety, the challenges unique to online environments, and the coping strategies students use to manage stress. Qualitative research design was used with semi-structured interviews of purposive sampled interviewees. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the collected data, and the analysis has made it possible to identify the major themes which were fear of committing linguistic errors, lack of nonverbal feedback, technological challenges, feeling of self-consciousness when using a camera, and lack of confidence because of inadequate practice in English. The evidence shows that online presentations produce a compounded effect of lingo, psychological and technological stressors that are in most cases more intense as compared to when in a traditional face-to-face environment. The strategies that students employed to cope with the anxiety included repeated practice, preparation of notes and digital tools, but these could only partially help them with the anxiety. The paper indicates that effective teaching strategies, guided oral practice and technological instructions must be encouraged to eliminate anxiety. The findings help elucidate the phenomenon of anxiety about online presentation better and have practical implications on ESL teachers and curriculum developers.

Keywords: *ESL Students, Language Anxiety, Online Presentations, Thematic Analysis*

1. INTRODUCTION

The English language proficiency is a key to the academic success of undergraduate students who learn English as a Second Language (ESL). It gives learners the opportunity to be an active part of the classroom discussions, learn course materials, and accomplish academic tasks that demand efficient communication. The scholars have also stressed that a high level of English proficiency leads to improved academic outcomes and the development of more confidence in the study setting (Krashen, 2013; Lightbown and Spada, 2020). In the case of ESL undergraduates, becoming proficient is not just a linguistic objective, but it is also a prerequisite to success in a university environment where English is a dominant language of instruction.

Higher education has made extensive use of presentations to evaluate the knowledge of the subject and the critical thinking of the students in communication skills. Presentations are a learning strategy; which ESL students can use to rehearse speaking English and to convey academic thoughts. Nevertheless, it has also been demonstrated in some studies that presentations can be the cause of anxiety because of linguistic pressure, because of the fear of being judged and because of lack of confidence in speaking (Horwitz et al., 1986; Woodrow, 2006). Delivering a speech in the classroom may be especially challenging to ESL students who might be afraid of pronunciation, grammar, and mistakes. Hence, classroom presentations have been a major setting, where the

language anxiety has been observable.

ESL students have been provided with new obstacles in online presentations since the face-to-face classroom has quickly become a digital platform following COVID-19. Online environments are not only flexible; they produce specific sources of anxiety as well as unstable internet connections, the lack of familiar presentation tools and less nonverbal responses of the audience (Dhawan, 2020; Karasmanaki and Tsantopoulos, 2021). Most students do not feel at ease about presenting to a screen rather than to actual human beings, and some find additional stress in having to deal with technology in addition to language performance. Consequently, online presentations have been a significant field of inquiry on how ESL learners undergo language anxiety during online learning. Exploration of these experiences can assist teachers in developing strategies to assist students, as well as, lessen anxiety associated with online communication activities.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The issue of language anxiety has been widely known as the main problem to successful communication among English as a Second Language learners. Anxious students usually find it difficult to convey their thoughts, become stuttering during the speaking process, and become unconfident in communicative situations in an academic environment (Horwitz et al., 1986). This anxiety is greater in activities involving oral performance like presentations since learners develop pressure associated with the consistency of pronunciation, grammatical accuracy and worry about negative critique (Woodrow, 2006). Due to this, language anxiety may restrict the students in their capability of engagements in academic activities and influence their general academic performances.

Despite the numerous studies that have addressed the concept of language anxiety in standard classroom presentation set-ups, there exists dearth of research that has studied the concept of language anxiety when it comes to online presentations in particular amongst undergraduate students of the ESL language. There have been brought about fresh challenges by the transition to digital learning settings such as technological problems, lack of interaction with the audience and presentation in unfamiliar environments, which can cause anxiety in different ways than face-to-face presentations (Dhawan, 2020). Nonetheless, the experiences of ESL undergraduates in making an online presentation are not adequately recorded in available literature. This gap presents the need to research the impact of online presentation contexts on language anxiety and how students experience and cope with these issues in virtual academic contexts.

1.2 Research Objectives

1. To explore ESL students' experiences of language anxiety during online presentations
2. To identify factors contributing to anxiety
3. To examine strategies students use to cope with anxiety

1.3 Research Questions

1. What are the experiences of ESL students regarding language anxiety in online presentations?
2. Which factors contribute to this anxiety?
3. How do students manage or cope with language anxiety?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The study is important as it contributes to the literature body of knowledge on the subject of language anxiety with its emphasis on the experience of ESL undergraduate students of online presentations anxiety. Although the topic of language anxiety has been extensively studied in the traditional classroom setting, the transition to online learning has triggered numerous new challenges in communication, which are yet to be comprehended. The study also provides valuable contributions that may allow researchers and educators to gain a better insight into how online presentation settings can affect second-language communication by investigating the feelings, challenges, and coping mechanisms of students during online communication (Dhawan, 2020; Karasmanaki and Tsantopoulos, 2021).

The research is also useful practically to teachers, curriculum designers and universities. The results can inform educators to create supportive methods that will decrease anxiety, including the clarity of instructions, practice, and the utilization of user-friendly digital tools. Knowledge about the exact causes of anxiety when presenting online will allow curriculum designers to adjust course designs, evaluation techniques, and learning tasks to provide ESL students with more comfortable learning conditions. When teachers are aware of the emotional and linguistic difficulties students have, it is possible to develop intervention strategies that enhance communicative skills, confidence and the overall academic outcomes (Horwitz et al., 1986). Thus, the research could inform research and practice in the teaching field and promote the creation of more accommodating and efficient online learning.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Concept of Language Anxiety

The concept of language anxiety is usually referred to as a specific state of tension, worry or nervousness, which is directly related to the use of a second or foreign language in either learning or communicative context. Most initial literature viewed language anxiety as a particular, situational anxiety that can be differentiated out of a general anxiety tendency (trait anxiety) possessed by the individual and a temporary, momentary anxiety (state anxiety) that occurs in a specific situation (Spielberger et al., 1983; MacIntyre and Gardner, 1991). In their study, Horwitz and other researchers defined foreign language classroom anxiety as a specific construct, which is a composite of communication apprehension, test anxiety and fear of negative evaluation; this theory has led to numerous studies on the impact of anxiety on language learning and performance (Horwitz et al., 1986). It is empirically known that speaking tasks are one of the most anxiety-inducing activities of language learners; nervous students are reluctant to participate in it, are less inclined to use complex forms, do not want to engage in it willingly; consequently, the lack of these activities reduces the chances of practicing and is detrimental to the development (Woodrow, 2006). The context-specific measures have also been created by the researchers, that is, the situation-specific measures like scales of speaking anxiety, foreign language classroom anxiety, etc., to reflect the situation-specific changes in anxiety, including oral presentations (MacIntyre and Gardner, 1991; Woodrow, 2006). Concisely, the literature demonstrates that language anxiety is a complex phenomenon that has significance in the immediate oral performance of the learners as well as their language development in the long run.

2.2 Online Presentations and ESL Learning

The transition to online instruction and testing has altered the situation under which oral activities are performed and brought about new challenges to ESL students. Online presentations are mediated by technology as compared to face-to-face presentations and tend to decrease the immediate, two-way nonverbal feedback that presenters get, which can further detach presenters and make them feel more self-conscious (Ruth, 2025). Poor internet connection, lack of familiarity with the software interface and fear of screen-sharing or recording are all technical issues that offer an additional stress factor that would otherwise be absent in traditional classrooms (Dhawan, 2020; Kabilan et al., 2022). A number of recent researches have reported that online format has relieved some students and a number have expressed greater anxiety since the camera can serve as a buffer, whereas others have said that they experience greater anxiety since they need to balance between technology and production in a language, these mixed results indicate that online presentation anxiety is multi-dimensional and may be affected by other factors, including digital competence, perceived audience, and previous experience with online platforms (Apridayani, 2024; Ruth, 2025). Since most traditional indices of language anxiety have been designed in the classroom setting, researchers have urged researchers to conduct more studies, which would investigate the interaction effect of online characteristics (such as the ability to see oneself, chat, and recording) and language anxiety when performing oral tasks. This literature is particularly significant to ESL undergraduates, in whose case oral presentation will be an item of assessment and professionalization; familiarity with the peculiarities of affording and stressing online presentations can assist teachers to develop better support and assessment practices in online education (Dhawan,

2020; Woodrow, 2006).

2.3 Coping Strategies for Language Anxiety

Scholars have established various coping mechanisms that can be used by learners to overcome language anxiety particularly in activities that require speaking and presenting in English. The psychological approaches are aimed at minimizing the emotional strain of oral performance. These are deep breathing, positive self-talk, practicing relaxation and positive self-confidence by being exposed to speaking activities repeatedly. Research has revealed that those learners who took cognitive reframing, that is, thinking of the presentation as a learning experience, not as a form of test, were found to experience less anxiety (MacIntyre and Gregersen, 2012). Similarly, students that have emotional support provided by teachers and peers tend to feel much safer and better whenever it comes to speaking (Jee, 2020). These psychological techniques emphasize the need to control emotions as well as develop language skills.

Pedagogical strategies refer to modifications in teaching, classroom practice, which aids in anxiety reduction. Scaffolding presentations may happen when the teachers provide practice sessions, clear instructions, model effective speaking behaviors and give positive and constructive feedback. Anxiety can also be reduced through friendly classroom settings, activities involving communication and group presentations that give the sense of shared responsibility (Kondo and Yang, 2004). Even with ESL learners, the systematic speaking activities and frequent opportunities to rehearse the presentation have proven to enhance confidence levels as well as fluency (Woodrow, 2006). Pedagogical strategies thus focus on the role played by instructors in reducing stress in the students and equipping them with oral communication skills.

With the emergence of online learning environments, technological strategies have become very crucial. Such tools as screen-recording software, online rehearsal websites, and digital cue cards enable students to rehearse before speaking in real-life situations to help them gain confidence. Other learner's lower anxiety levels by disabling the self-view when giving online presentation, use of virtual background to feel more at ease, or use of supportive tools such as chat box to engage with the audience (Apridayani, 2024). Nevertheless, technological strategies are not always associated with pure benefits since less digitally literate students might become overwhelmed with them, thus becoming more anxious than being less so (Dhawan, 2020). This demonstrates that the support of technology requires close integration and training.

Though, there is an increase in the coping strategy research, there are still gaps that remain significant to the literature. A large part of the available literature addresses the conventional presentation in the classroom, and the number of articles investigating special coping mechanisms in the context of online presentation anxiety by ESL undergraduates is lower. The peculiarities of virtual environment, such as the pressure of cameras, unreliable internet connection, absence of nonverbal communication and combined use of language and technology, are not discussed entirely in earlier studies (Ruth, 2025). Further, few studies investigate the effectiveness of psychological, pedagogical and technological strategies used together as a way of helping learners in an integrated manner. The perception of students regarding the utility of such strategies in the online environment is not well understood. Such gaps demonstrate that more research is required on the effective strategies to apply to online presentation environments with ESL learners.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The research design adopted in this study is a qualitative research design since the research seek to understand the personal experiences and emotions and perceptions of ESL undergraduate students concerning the language anxiety in online presentations. Qualitative study suits well in comprehending how people perceive and interpret their experiences that are involved in matters that are of psychological and emotional nature like anxiety. The thematic analysis is used as the primary data analysis approach in the study. Thematic analysis is also good as it enables the researcher to come up with patterns, categories and themes that are natural due to the answers of the participants. This design offers an adaptable method that is useful in capturing the intricacies and richness of the feelings and challenges experienced by the students when the presentations are done online.

3.2 Population and Sampling

The sample population that has been used in this study is the undergraduate students who are English Second Language learners. The suitability of such learners is attributed to the fact that they often take part in online academic work and are likely to develop anxiety associated with languages when making a presentation. The research design employs the purposive sampling design and this implies that the respondents have been identified according to certain attributes that have a bearing to the study. Here, the students should have been exposed to giving online presentation in the English language. Qualitative studies are best suited to purposive sampling since the sample will be able to give profound and valuable information regarding the study subject. The sample size has been taken to roughly 15 participants because the size is deemed enough to conduct qualitative research, and it would enable an exploration in detail, and at the same time the data would be manageable to analyze.

3.3 Data Collection Method

The data, semi-structured interviews have been used and this helps participants to express their experiences freely and at the same time direct the discussion in areas that are important to language anxiety and online presentations. Semi structured interviews are open ended and enable the researcher to seek further clarifications where necessary. Each of the interviews was held online using such platforms as Zoom or Google Meet at the discretion of the participants. The interviews have been audio-recorded with permission so as to be accurate. The verbatim transcripts of the interviews have been obtained after every interview. Transcription enables the researcher to go through the words of the participants word by word and no crucial details would be overlooked in the process of the study.

4.4 Data Analysis

The data that was collected have been analyzed using thematic analysis. This would start with familiarization, in which the researcher reads the transcripts multiple times to be acquainted with the content. Once this has been done, preliminary codes are created by finding any significant units of information in the text. These codes are then categorized into bigger groups depending on their similarities. Based on these types, the major themes and subthemes are elaborated to reflect the major ideas which emerge out of the experiences of the participants. Lastly, the themes will be analyzed considering the research questions, literature and theoretical concepts in existence.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Thematic analysis enables the researcher to make sense of complicated emotional and linguistic experiences and serve the results in an organized and significant manner.

3.5 Ethical Considerations

In this study, critical ethical considerations are adhered to in an effort to safeguard the participants and their rights. Before the data collection data has been collected, informed consent has been obtained. The purpose of the study, procedures, and voluntary nature of the participants have been communicated to them in a straightforward manner and their choice to participate and pull out of the study at any time and without any consequences. The privacy of all data has been guaranteed because only the researcher can access it. The anonymity has been preserved by eliminating names, student IDs and any other identification data in the transcripts and final report. Rather, pseudonyms or participant codes have been applied. These ethical provisions aid in establishment of safe environment where students feel free to express themselves freely and frankly about their experience.

4. FINDINGS

The transcripts of the interviews were analyzed finding that there were a few significant themes on how ESL undergraduate students react to language anxiety when making an online presentation. These themes are associated with emotions of students, language barriers, technical problems, and the coping mechanism that students employed to deal with their anxiety. Even though the individual experiences were different, the majority of students referred to online presentations as tense and language intensive. Each of the themes has been described below with example statements.

4.1 Theme 1: Fear of Making Mistakes in English

One of the biggest discoveries was that students had often been concerned about committing grammatical, pronunciation and vocabulary errors during their online presentation. They were afraid of the mistakes they could commit to be less competent in English. Most of the students said that this fear worsened when they were aware that the presentation was being recorded since they could watch the mistakes again. For example, one participant said, *“When I speak, I keep thinking that my pronunciation is wrong. I know the teacher and my classmates are listening, so I become very nervous and forget the correct words.”* Another student shared, *“Online presentations make it worse because the recording scares me. I feel I cannot correct myself once it is saved.”* These examples show that the fear of linguistic errors remains one of the strongest triggers of language anxiety in online settings.

4.2 Theme 2: Limited Nonverbal Feedback Increases Anxiety

Students have claimed that there is less eye contact, facial expression, and instant response of the audience when they are presenting online. Such absence of real-time feedback meant that they were not certain that their message was getting across or that the listeners were getting them. One participant explained, *“In the classroom I can see people’s faces, but online I cannot know if they are confused or bored. This makes me speak faster because I want to finish quickly.”* Another said, *“When everyone turns off their camera, I feel like I am talking to myself. It makes me more nervous.”* These statements show that the absence of visual cues contributes significantly to communication anxiety.

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Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

4.3 Theme 3: Technological Problems Intensify Anxiety

Another important theme was technology-related problems. Lack of good internet connectivity, microphone issues, background noise, and unexpected software issues were the reasons students were anxious about. These problems gave them the fear that their performance will be interrupted or graded negatively. One student shared, *“My internet stops in the middle of speaking, and then I panic because I lose my flow.”* Another stated, *“I worry that my voice will not be clear. Sometimes the audio breaks, and I think the teacher will think I am not prepared.”* Such examples show that technical unpredictability adds an extra layer of stress that is unique to online presentations.

4.4 Theme 4: Increased Self-Consciousness Due to Camera Use

The fact that many students were not comfortable to turn on their cameras made them more attentive to their looks, background and facial expression. They believed that physically being on the screen enhanced their anxiety. One participant explained, *“When my camera is on, I feel everyone is looking at my face and judging me. It makes me forget what I practiced.”* Another mentioned, *“I try to look at the slides, but the small box showing my own face distracts me. I feel more pressure.”* These experiences show that the camera itself becomes a source of psychological stress.

4.5 Theme 5: Lack of Practice and Low Confidence in English

Most of the respondents mentioned that they did not speak English often when they were not in a classroom. This reduced their confidence in making presentations over the internet. Due to the online classes, the students did not spend as much time interacting with others in person, which means that some students felt they did not get the chance to practice their speaking skills. One student said, *“We don't speak English at home, so when the teacher asks me to present, I feel scared. Online classes give us fewer chances to practice.”* Another mentioned, *“I am not confident in English, so even small sentences make me nervous in online presentations.”* This indicates that low self-confidence remains a major factor contributing to language anxiety.

4.6 Theme 6: Coping Strategies Used by Students

There were many coping methodologies that students adopted to deal with their anxiety. Others rehearsed their presentations several times before going on line whereas others had full scripts so as not to forget important points. Some students stated that they read better when on the screen to avoid the pressure. One participant stated, *“I practice in front of the mirror many times. It helps me feel more confident.”* Another explained, *“I keep my notes beside the screen so I do not forget. It makes me less nervous.”* Some students also relied on technological tools such as pronunciation apps or online dictionaries to prepare more effectively.

5. DISCUSSION

The results of the present study indicate that ESL undergraduate learners have a significant level of language anxiety when making online presentations. The results support and build upon the existing studies on the experiences of anxiety in language acquisition in second language. Among the most predominant trends in the data is the fact that the students are afraid of making mistakes in pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary and this makes them nervous when giving presentations.

Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

This is in line with Horwitz et al. (1986) who elaborate that negative assessment fear is one of the leading causes of the foreign language classroom anxiety. In the same way, Woodrow (2006) discovered that, learners tend to develop high anxiety particularly in oral presentations as a result of their apprehension of being evaluated based on the accuracy of their languages. These previous findings are upheld in the current study and indicate that these fears persist online. The other key discovery is that lack of nonverbal communication in online presentation makes students nervous. The respondents stated that audience responses were uninterpretable since most of the classmates turned off their cameras, or the layout of the screen did not allow them to look at each other. This aligns with the findings of Apridayani (2024), who also found that online platforms lower the degree of interaction and establish communication barriers among presenters. The current research thus proves the point that the online learning environment alters the communication nature and heightens anxiety of ESL students. Another theme that was unique and important is technology related stress. Lack of internet connections, sound problems, and sudden malfunctions were the reasons why students were nervous. Dhawan (2020) also documented that technical issues and digital illiteracy tend to cause pressure to students in distance learning. The present paper reinforces this point by demonstrating that these issues are even more crucial under the conditions of online performance when any one inconvenience can disrupt the whole performance. The other important observation is that students were not comfortable using cameras due to their increased self-consciousness in terms of body language and looks. This finding builds upon the results of Karasmanaki and Tsantopoulos (2021), who mentioned that students tend to be stressed when constantly on the screen in an online classroom. The current study further contributes to the fact that this stress increases more in presentation where the face of the speaker is still in the limelight. The findings also indicate that anxiety is enhanced by absence of real-life English practice. Those students who use English infrequently outside the classroom are not confident enough and feel that they are unprepared to give a presentation. It is in line with MacIntyre and Gregersen (2012), who claim that the low language confidence directly raises learner anxiety. Nevertheless, the results also indicate that online classes can decrease the chances of speaking in an informal situation that has not been studied as extensively in the previous research. Therefore, the present study can add a new dimension as it demonstrates that the lack of interaction in online classes can indirectly increase presentation anxiety among ESL students.

Some of the coping mechanisms employed by the students like rehearsing, taking notes or even using online resources resemble those proposed by Kondo and Yang (2004) who concluded that students tend to manage the anxiety through preparation and positive thought. The presented research contributes to this knowledge by demonstrating that despite the effectiveness of these strategies, students still believe that they need more teacher assistance, more clarity and more practice. On the whole, the results of the given research indicate a high level of congruence with other studies done in the field but also demonstrate the new issues peculiar to online presentations, particularly, technology-related stress, camera pressure and absence of interaction. The additions imply the necessity of new instruction in the online environment to decrease anxiety levels and promote better support of ESL learners.

6. CONCLUSION

In this study, the authors examine the experiences of ESL undergraduate students with language anxiety when making online presentations. According to the findings, online presentations generate

a complex of linguistic, psychological and technological problems that increase the anxiety of learners. Among the significant contributors to the stress, students mentioned fear of error, low confidence and insufficient practice with English as well as being uncomfortable with the camera. The problem with the technology like inadequate internet connectivity and software glitches also heightened anxiety. Even though repeated practice, note preparation, and online tools are some of the coping strategies that were employed by students, they did not always have a full effect. In general, the research demonstrates that online presentation anxiety is a complex phenomenon that cannot be compared to the classroom anxiety and requires specific intervention to help ESL students in online learning environments.

7. Implications and Recommendations

The results have a number of significant implications on educators, curriculum designers, and institutions. To start with, educators should establish good online learning platforms which do not instill in students the fear of being judged negatively. This is through the clear instructions, allowing one to rehearse presentation, constructive feedback and peer support. Second, the curriculum designers are to include more systematic oral practice in online classes, so that the students have frequent opportunities to master fluency and confidence in the English language. Third, the digital literacy and the use of online platforms in institutions should be trained, and this allows students to handle technical difficulties that foster anxiety.

Pedagogically, video practice, rehearsal, and guided scripts are some of the strategies that can enable students to gain confidence gradually before they can present themselves live. Small group presentations and encouragement of multiple attempts by teachers are also options that allow them to reduce the pressure associated with formal assessment. Lastly, further investigations into the combination of psychological, pedagogical, and technological interventions to produce an integrated system of support towards students along with the study of online presentation anxiety in bigger and more heterogeneous ESL groups should be pursued in the future. Such recommendations can be applied to enhance experiences of online presentations of students, improve their language learning results, and help them to develop as a whole in their academic performance.

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Liberal Journal of Language & Literature Review

Print ISSN: 3006-5887

Online ISSN: 3006-5895

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